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EVALUATION OF EFFECTIVENESS OF THE LASER ENDOSCOPIC LARYNGOPLASTY IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC PARALYTIC STENOSIS OF THE LARYNX

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Chronic stenosis of the larynx (CSL) is a group of diseases which is the main symptom of is persistent narrowing of the larynx lumen, disrupting the flow of air into the respiratory tract, leading to the development of obstructive respiratory failure, as well as pronounced impairment of the voice function. One of the types of stenosis is paralytic stenosis of the larynx (PSL), in which the narrowing of the larynx lumen is associated with a disorder of motor function in the form of a decrease in the strength/amplitude of voluntary movements (paresis) or their complete absence (paralysis) due to a violation of the innervation of the corresponding muscles of the larynx.

The aim of the study was to evaluate the effectiveness of laser endoscopic laryngoplasty in patients with chronic bilateral paralytic laryngeal stenosis.

Materials and methods of study: We observed 22 patients with chronic bilateral paralytic stenosis of the larynx, from 22 to 66 years old at Tashkent state dental institute, Otorhinolaryngology department during 2017 to 2020. From observed patients 16 of them were female and 6 were male. In 11 patients in anamnesis was carried out surgery on the thyroid gland, in other patients were not provided thyroid gland surgery.

Evaluation of effectiveness of the treatment was carried out on the basis of general clinical data, standard otorhinolaryngological examination, video endostroboscopy, fibrolaryngoscopy, spirometry.

Results: According to the data of endoscopic research methods, the vocal folds of the patients were in the paramedian position before the surgical treatment. In 7 of them, cicatricial changes were revealed in the area of the interscapular part of the larynx, in 4 patients, scars and

granulations were noted in the sublining space, above and around the tracheostomy tube.

In the surgical treatment of patients with chronic paralytic stenosis of the larynx, we used the method of laser endoscopic submucosal chordaritenoidotomy. A diode laser with a wavelength of 980 nm was used in the contact mode.

On the second day after the operation, all patients noted an improvement in breathing. During fibrolaryngoscopy and video endostroboscopy, the following dynamics of the laryngoscopic picture was observed: during the first 48 hours after the operation, there was edema of the mucous membrane in the area of the surgical intervention. On the 3rd-7th day after the operation, the edema of the laryngeal mucosa decreased significantly, on the 10th-14th day, reactive inflammation in the larynx was minimal.

In the long-term postoperative period (after 4-6 months), we examined 9 patients. With video endostroboscopy: the glottis is triangular; during phonation, the anterior 2/3 of the vocal fold on the side of the operation performed touch the contralateral side, which provides a sonorous voice.

Thus, the Laser submucosal chordaritenoidotomy is a gentle method of surgical treatment due to the fact that the volume of the resected tissues is optimal for the formation of a lumen of the larynx sufficient for breathing and preservation of the voice and protective function of the larynx.